

The Impacts of Youtube Videos on EFL Juniors' Listening Skill at Nguyen Tat Thanh University

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ABSTRACT: Using YouTube videos in English learning has become popular in recent years. This study investigates the impact of YouTube videos on EFL juniors' listening skill at Nguyen Tat Thanh University, Vietnam. It contributes to improving students' listening skill. The paper conducts a mixed-method approach, including a quantitative survey on eighty juniors and a qualitative in-depth interview with five random participants. The survey provides data on attendees' attitudes towards watching YouTube videos in listening skill improvement. Meanwhile, the interview offers deeper insights into the challenges and benefits that these videos have brought to them. The findings reveal positive effects of YouTube clips on their listening skill development through examining the survey's results and exploring the interview's information. The study highly conducts YouTube videos' potential benefits in teaching and learning listening skill. Further research is suggested to discover its long-term effects on the other language skills such as speaking and writing ones.

KEYWORDS: YouTube videos, listening skill, EFL juniors, Nguyen Tat Thanh University.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The background of the study

For over the last decade, YouTube videos have become one of the most popular resources for entertainment and learning. Millions of people use them for different purposes, among which is for English learning. Many people find that YouTube videos can help students improve their listening skill. They supplies learners various English clips in different topic. This is a good chance for students to practice and develop their listening skill. As indicated by Afrizal and Herlina (2023), YouTube videos may be used as a supportive and educational resource to enhance students' listening skill. Many students may acquire English language skills by watching brief English films, videos, and instructional materials.

Besides, Yuyun and Simamora (2021) have ever asserted that YouTube videos encourage students to enhance their learning interests. In terms of linguistics, YouTube videos help them improve listening skill by using a familiar language and predicting speakers' expressions and gestures. They also assist learners to know other countries' cultures and broaden their vocabulary. In terms of non-linguistic aspects, YouTube videos motivate them to learn listening skill by fostering their motivation and focus. Therefore, it can be seen that YouTube videos may be a useful learning resource for students to improve their language skills, particularly their listening ability.

Unfortunately, a great number of students have not recognized YouTube's wonderful benefits in English language learning yet. They often use its videos for recreation rather than for learning purposes. Particularly, they watch them just for fun in their free time. They have not paid much attention to exploiting its clips for listening activities. That is the reason why this article examines whether YouTube videos really bring great positive aspects to learners in their listening classes. Also, the study explores students' attitudes towards using YouTube videos in improving their listening ability. Currently, there are no researches about the impact of YouTube videos on juniors' listening skill at Nguyen Tat Thanh University, Vietnam. Thus, the study is conducted to answer three following questions:

- (1) To what extent can YouTube videos improve EFL juniors' listening skill?
- (2) What are students' perspectives on using YouTube videos in listening activities?
- (3) What challenges do students deal with while using YouTube videos in listening classes?

1.2 Aim of the study

This research aims at investigating how YouTube videos affect the listening skill of EFL juniors at Nguyen Tat Thanh University. The

study also wants to discover students' perspectives and experiences on using its videos into their listening skill improvement.

1.3 Significance of the study

The study can firstly help teachers and students see great benefits of YouTube videos in English language learning, particularly in improving EFL juniors' listening skill at Nguyen Tat Thanh University. Secondly, the results of the study can change both teachers' and student's attitudes toward YouTube videos, especially the ones who have negative ideas on it.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of YouTube

YouTube has developed into a worldwide academic and informal learning platform. Unlike conventional media learning tools, YouTube is a social media platform with a variety of features that reveal its real educational importance (Shoufan & Mohamed, 2022). Users can create and share materials on the social networking site, YouTube. According to Abidin & Ngadiman (2021), YouTube contains an invaluable resource for EFL speaking instruction. It allows learners to acquire proficiency in languages throughout the world. It provides English lessons, movies, and daily conversations, thereby helping learners access useful knowledge. Consequently, it can be said that YouTube has emerged as a great platform for the instruction and acquisition of English, offering a wide range of perspectives and activities to EFL students, and improving their proficiency in listening.

2.2 Overview of listening skill

Listening is an essential language ability that must be cultivated throughout the process of acquiring a second language (Gilakjani and Sabouri, 2016). Listening skill refers to the ability to perceive and comprehend the spoken words of others. Although listening is significant, language learners see it as the most challenging language skill to acquire. In the same way, a lot of teachers fail to prioritize listening comprehension in their courses (Saehu, 2016).

Listening is recognized as an important component of language learning and teaching since it is required in the communication process (Fussalam et al., 2019). Good listening skill will make conversations more exciting and successful due to speakers' actively conversational engagement. The effective communication occurs when there is an interaction sufficiently between participants. Listening aids them in understanding and comprehending ideas presented.

According to Rohaniyah and Nasrullah (2022), listening is a complex skill that requires students to listen and transfer information through auditory insight. It demands them the most effort to recognize spoken text, unlike written one, which can be easily understood. Listening comprehension is a cognitive process where people actively concentrate on particular aspects of auditory information, create meaning from passages, and connect what they hear to their existing knowledge.

2.3 The importance of the listening skill

Listening is a crucial language skill that enhances success and satisfaction. It involves receptivity, understanding and partnership in communication. Good listening is essential for society as it is an integral part of the communication process. A good listener can manipulate sounds into words, relate meanings to experiences and share responsibility. Academically, listening skill is vital for both students and teachers. Enhancing listening skill in one's life and attitude is a steppingstone towards becoming a better speaker (Sadiku, 2015). In addition, listening is an important activity that involves identifying, understanding, and interpreting spoken languages. It helps students be aware of language usage, creatively use grammar, and gain detailed comprehension.

2.4 Related studies

There have been some previous researches on the improvement of the listening skill and the use of YouTube videos as a language learning aid. Particularly, Silviyanti (2014) researched to determine whether both within and outside of the classroom, students were interested in using its videos to enhance their listening abilities. Forty-five students in a Listening III class were assessed using open and closed questionnaires. The most solid evidence for utilizing YouTube videos was determined to be its advantages to their English, curiosity, and applicability to in-class subjects. The least motivated students were those who used the videos to learn English outside of classroom. Open responses to YouTube videos included watching native speakers, comprehending themes, and locating relevant contents. However, negative replies included a lack of internet access at home, a lack of willingness to study alone, and not being given homework. Despite these problems, YouTube videos may be seen as a helpful resource for

listening lessons owing to its multiple advantages.

Ayu (2016) and Qomariyah et al. (2021) did research on the impact of YouTube videos on students' listening comprehension. Their sample was undergraduate learners from the University. The findings revealed a strong effect of its videos on listening comprehension. All of participants agreed that its clips made listening courses more interesting. The results indicated that utilizing audio-visual media helped students improve their listening skill and make listening classes more enjoyable.

Yuyun and Simamora (2021) conducted another research on the use of YouTube videos as a teaching aid for enhancing listening comprehension abilities among EFL students. The research included eight participants from a private institution in Jakarta, who were interviewed and observed in class. The findings revealed that YouTube videos boost students' confidence, pleasure, and interest in studying, making the process more interesting and engaging. The research highlighted the significance of combining authentic resources and ICT in the classroom to aid the teaching-learning process.

The studies above are on using YouTube videos as a teaching and learning supporting resource in improving students' listening performance. However, the studies reveal some drawbacks that the articles have not taken into consideration yet. Particularly, their samples are too small to make sure that their results are reliable. Additionally, there have been no researches on using YouTube videos conducted at Nguyen Tat Thanh University, Vietnam. Thus, it is an impetus to carry out this paper.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Participants

The participants of this study were 80 EFL juniors randomly selected at Nguyen Tat Thanh University. Among these students, there were 33 males (41.2%), 47 females (58.8%); the number of students aging from 20 to 22 was 61 (76.3%), from 23 to 24 was 16 (20.0%) and from 25 to 26 was 3 (3.7%). The number of years students learnt English was diverse. Dominantly, 45 participants learnt English from 6 to 10 years; 30 other learners studied this language over 10 years; and 05 ones left studied it from 1 to 5 years. This can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Students' information

Table with 6 columns: Gender, Age, and Years of learning English. It contains data for Male and Female students, categorized by age groups (20-22, 23-24, 25-26) and years of learning English (1-5, 6-10, over 10).

3.2 Data collection

The study used a questionnaire with 21 items to collect information quantitatively. Its three first questions were about the students' information: age, gender, years of learning English; and the eighteen ones left were related to (1) Students' attitudes towards watching YouTube videos on listening skill improvement, (2) students' opinion on watching YouTube videos toward vocabulary improvement, and (3) some challenges students deal with using YouTube videos. Besides, the research randomly chose five students to carry out an in-depth interview. The contents of the interview also focused on three matters mentioned above. This process was conducted from February to March, 2024 on eighty EFL juniors in academic year 2023 – 2024 at Nguyen Tat Thanh University, Vietnam.

3.3 Data analysis

To analyze the quantitative data taken from the questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale including (1): Strongly disagree (SD), (2): Disagree (D), (3): Neutral (N), (4): Agree (A), and (5): Strongly agree (SD), the study exploited SPSS 27.0 software to have information on percentage, mean and standard deviation and used Smart PLS 4.0 software to get values of Cronbach's alpha and correlations and impact coefficients among items. Besides, the qualitative data taken from the in-depth interview were conducted to clarify the benefits and some drawbacks of YouTube videos in the listening skill development.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

This section shows the results of the questionnaire and interview. It supplies a comprehensive view about the research matters through their findings.

4.1. Questionnaire’s results

To know whether the reliability and validity of items are statistically significant or not, the study ran Cronbach’s alphas, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of these items together (see Table 2 below).

Table 2. Analyze the construct reliability and validity

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
CH	0.969	0.970	0.975	0.866
SA	0.962	0.964	0.970	0.841
SO	0.970	0.970	0.975	0.868

(**CH**: challenges of using YouTube videos; **SA**: Students’ attitudes towards watching YouTube videos on listening skill improvement; **SO**: Students’ opinion on watching YouTube videos toward vocabulary improvement)

As recommended by Hair et al. (2022, p.118), in exploratory studies, the Composite Reliability (CR) should be from 0.6 or higher. For confirmatory studies, a threshold of 0.7 is considered appropriate for the CR value. Garson (2016) and Hair et al. (2022) added that a scale obtains a convergence if the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5 or higher. This threshold of 50% indicates that the latent variable will explain at least 50% of the variance in each observed variable on average. The results in Table 2 illustrate that all factor structures demonstrate good reliability, since both Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability (rho_c) coefficients are higher than 0.7. The results also reveal that the Composite Reliability (rho_c) is higher than Cronbach's alpha, which reflects significantly good reliability and validity of items.

Table 3. Analyze the outer loading of the research factors - Matrix

	CH	SA	SO
CH1	0.835		
CH2	0.931		
CH3	0.945		
CH4	0.972		
CH5	0.958		
CH6	0.937		
SA1		0.924	
SA2		0.896	
SA3		0.922	
SA4		0.956	
SA5		0.890	
SA6		0.915	
SO1			0.927
SO2			0.922
SO3			0.950
SO4			0.923
SO5			0.930
SO6			0.938

According to Hair et al. (2022, p.118), the acceptable point for the outer loading of observed variables is equal or greater than 0.7, which is considered a good value. If the outer loading is smaller than 0.7, it is seen a weak point and may not be reliable for measuring latent variables in PLS-SEM. When the outer loading value of a variable is below 0.7, it means that the indicator is not good enough to measure the corresponding latent variable. The results in Table 3 illustrate that these observed variables are higher than 0.7. Thus, these indicators significantly contribute to the research reliability and validity through the convergence of the outer loading in each cluster.

Table 4. Analyze Path coefficients

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	P values
CH -> SA	0.776	0.766	0.110	0.000
CH -> SO	0.762	0.757	0.137	0.000
CH1 <- CH	0.835	0.822	0.112	0.000
CH2 <- CH	0.931	0.925	0.031	0.000
CH3 <- CH	0.945	0.940	0.026	0.000
CH4 <- CH	0.972	0.970	0.013	0.000
CH5 <- CH	0.958	0.956	0.017	0.000
CH6 <- CH	0.937	0.933	0.032	0.000
SA1 <- SA	0.924	0.920	0.030	0.000
SA2 <- SA	0.896	0.886	0.046	0.000
SA3 <- SA	0.922	0.913	0.037	0.000
SA4 <- SA	0.956	0.952	0.019	0.000
SA5 <- SA	0.890	0.891	0.029	0.000
SA6 <- SA	0.915	0.906	0.040	0.000
SO1 <- SO	0.927	0.921	0.036	0.000
SO2 <- SO	0.922	0.915	0.038	0.000
SO3 <- SO	0.950	0.948	0.019	0.000
SO4 <- SO	0.923	0.917	0.033	0.000
SO5 <- SO	0.930	0.927	0.035	0.000
SO6 <- SO	0.938	0.933	0.026	0.000

Data in Table 4 shows that all P values of variables are 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05, a statistically significant level. Their impact coefficients of variables in the model are positive, which indicates the positive affected direction. Besides, as observed the ‘Original sample’ section, it can be seen that most impact relationships within each group of CH, SA and SO as well as between CH and SA and/or CH and SO are significant. Clearly, the impact indicator of CH on SA is 0.776 (77.6%), and that of CH on SO is 0.762 (76.2%). Meanwhile, the influence coefficients of CH cluster (CH1 to CH6) exceed from 0.835 to 0.972; those in SA group (SA1 to SA6) are from 0.890 to 0.956; and in SO (SO1 to SO6) from 0.922 to 0.950. In other words, the impact coefficients of variables in three groups above are very strong, stretching from 83.5% to 97.2% for CH; from 89.0% to 95.6% for SA; and from 92.2% to 95.0% for SO. In addition, the sample mean values of variables in each cluster are at high levels. Particularly, the mean values of the CH, SA and SO groups respectively spread from 0.822 to 0.970; from 0.886 to 0.952; and from 0.915 to 0.948.

4.1.1. Students’ attitudes towards watching YouTube videos on the listening skill improvement

Table 5. Students’ attitudes towards watching YouTube videos on the listening skill improvement

Likert’s scales	Watching YouTube videos helps me improve my listening skill [SA1].		Watching YouTube videos regularly makes me more proficient in spoken language [SA2].		I feel more confident in comprehending spoken English after watching YouTube videos consistently [SA3].		I can understand conversations of native speakers better due to watching YouTube videos frequently [SA4].		My listening ability has improved significantly since I applied YouTube videos into my learning routine [SA5].		The more time I watch YouTube videos, the much progress I have made in my listening skill [SA6].	
	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%
SD	3	3.8	4	5.0	4	5.0	4	5.0	4	5.0	4	5.0
D	0	0.0	1	1.3	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	1.3	0	0.0
N	8	10.0	10	12.5	7	8.7	9	11.2	11	13.7	5	6.3
A	42	52.5	39	48.7	42	52.5	38	47.5	34	42.5	41	51.2
SA	27	33.8	26	32.5	27	38.8	29	36.3	30	37.5	30	37.5
Total	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100
Mean	4.13		4.03		4.10		4.10		4.06		4.16	
Std. Dev.	.877		.981		.936		.963		1.011		.934	

As could be seen data from Table 5, a majority of participants (86.3%) found that watching YouTube videos helps them improve their listening skill. They (83.8%) also confirmed that watching its videos could frequently help them understand conversations of native speakers better. In addition, over four-fifths of students (81.2%) indicated that watching its clips regularly made them more proficient in spoken language. Remarkably, 91.3% of participants revealed that they felt more confident in comprehending spoken English after watching its videos consistently. Most of the respondents (88.7%) emphasized that the more time they watched its movies, the much progress they had made in their listening skill. Although the percentage of students decreased a little bit, there were still 80.0% of attendees saying that their listening ability had improved significantly since they applied its videos into their learning routine. Overall, most items’ means vibrated from 4.03 to 4.16. It could be said that a great number of students saw the positive impact of watching YouTube videos on listening skill improvement.

4.1.2 Students’ opinion on watching YouTube videos toward vocabulary improvement

Table 6. Students’ opinion on watching YouTube videos toward vocabulary improvement

Likert’s scales	Watching YouTube videos helps me learn new words in different topics [SO1].		YouTube videos contribute to expanding my vocabulary [SO2].		The settings in YouTube videos help me understand the meanings of new words easily [SO3].		I actively use new words learned from YouTube videos in my daily communication [SO4].		YouTube videos expose me to specialized vocabulary relevant to specific subjects or fields of interest [SO5].		I find that YouTube videos stimulate me to acquire new words quickly [SO6].	
	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%
SD	4	5.0	5	6.3	5	6.3	4	5.0	4	5.0	5	6.3
D	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	1.3	0	0.0
N	3	3.8	8	10.0	8	10.0	10	12.5	7	8.8	6	7.5

A	48	60.0	37	46.2	41	51.2	41	51.2	37	46.3	35	43.7
SA	25	31.3	30	37.5	26	32.5	25	31.3	31	38.8	34	42.5
Total	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100
Mean	4.13		4.09		4.04		4.04		4.13		4.16	
Std. Dev.	.891		1.021		.999		.947		.986		1.024	

Data in Table 6 shows students' opinion on watching YouTube videos toward vocabulary improvement. As could be seen that most students (91.3%) agreed that watching YouTube videos helped them learn new words in different topics. 83.7% of them found that its videos contributed to expanding their vocabulary. The number of respondents (86.2%) reported that the videos stimulated them to acquire new words quickly. A smaller proportion of the participants (83.7%) said that the settings in its clips helped them understand the meanings of new words easily. Most students said that the videos exposed them to specialized vocabulary relevant to specific subjects or fields of their interest, which accounted for 85.1%. Meanwhile, the least proportion in this group (82.5%) shared that they actively used new words learned from YouTube videos in their daily communication. In general, most items showed that their means vibrated from 3.92 to 4.04. This indicated that the participants saw great benefits of watching its videos on their vocabulary improvement.

4.1.3 Some challenges of using YouTube videos

Table 7. Some challenges of using YouTube videos

Likert's scales	It takes me much time to watch YouTube videos [CH1].		Not all YouTube videos are suitable for my English level [CH2].		Watching YouTube videos too long makes me tired and fainted [CH3].		I take time to find suitable YouTube videos with my learning topic [CH4].		The contents of many YouTube videos are sometimes too violent to enjoy [CH5].		Speakers in many YouTube videos talk too fast to catch their points [CH6].	
	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%	N ₀	%
SD	4	5.0	3	3.8	3	3.8	3	3.8	3	3.8	3	3.8
D	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	1.3
N	5	6.3	9	11.2	8	10.0	5	6.3	9	11.2	9	11.2
A	47	58.7	42	52.5	47	58.7	45	56.2	41	51.3	44	55.0
SA	24	30.0	26	32.5	22	27.5	27	33.7	27	33.7	23	28.7
Total	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100	80	100
Mean	4.09		4.10		4.06		4.16		4.11		4.04	
Std. Dev.	.903		.880		.847		.849		.886		.892	

As can be seen Table 7 above that most of participants (88.7%) admitted that watching YouTube videos took them a lot of time. 85.0% of respondents indicated that not all its videos were suitable for their English level. Likewise, they (85.0%) added that the contents of many videos were sometimes too violent to enjoy. Additionally, a great number of students (86.2%) shared that watching its clips too long made them tired and fainted. Another challenge that many students (89.9%) dealt with was that they took time to find suitable videos with their learning topic. Meanwhile, 83.7% of learners revealed that speakers in many clips talked too fast to catch their points. Therefore, it can be concluded that a majority of respondents recognized some drawbacks of using YouTube videos on their English learning, especially on their listening skill development. This can be proved through mean values of items stretching from 4.04 to 4.16 stated in Table 6.

4.2 Interview's results

The interview was conducted on five EFL juniors at Nguyen Tat Thanh University. Each conversation lasted from ten to fifteen minutes and was recorded by the smart phone. The following information was mainly extracted from the recordings.

4.2.1 The students' attitudes toward YouTube videos in their listening skill improvement

The interview: In your opinion, can YouTube videos help you improve your listening skill?

Student 1: Well, I find that my listening skill has been improved considerably since I watched YouTube videos. I can predict new words different contexts thanks to various settings. I gradually improve my pronunciation, too.

Student 2: Sure. Personally I think YouTube videos are very helpful. I can understand what people have said in simple situations. Especially, whenever I do not catch the speakers' points, I can replay its videos.

Student 3: Definitely. I can listen to various accents of native speakers. From that, I automatically adjust my pronunciation.

Student 4: Of course. YouTube videos are essential learning resources that I can see native speakers use English naturally. Gradually, I am familiar with their accent and pronunciation.

Student 5: Certainly. My listening skill has been improved a lot because I can watch English clips in on YouTube.

4.2.2 The pros and cons of YouTube videos on listening activities

The interview: Can you tell me some pros and cons of YouTube videos on your listening skill?

Student 1: Sure, I can choose appropriate videos with my learning topics and watch them at any time and any places I like. However, it takes me much time to select them.

Student 2: I am not afraid of missing videos on YouTube and I can watch them many times later. Conversely, where there is a weak internet connection, I cannot access to the link and watch videos.

Student 3: Well, I can watch YouTube videos at any time. However, if I watch them too much, I feel headache, which badly affects to my health and learning.

Student 4: Learning English through YouTube videos is convenient, but I find it takes much time to search for suitable videos with my learning goal.

Student 5: Sometimes the video contents on YouTube are inappropriate for learning environment. Thus, it takes me much time to choose them.

4.2.3 The challenges of using YouTube videos

The interview: Do you think that there are some challenges of using YouTube videos?

Student 1: Of course. There are different themes or topics (from good to bad) that YouTube videos discuss about. I have carefully selected suitable ones for my study. So, it takes me much time to find good one.

Student 2: The speakers often talk too fast for me to catch their ideas.

Student 3: Although YouTube videos are very useful for recreation, I am sometimes addicted to them.

Student 4: In many situations, I cannot listen to speakers in YouTube videos because their strange accents.

Student 5: Negative aspects of YouTube videos are violent clips, which badly affect to viewers.

5. DISCUSSIONS AND FINDINGS

From the questionnaire results, it could be found that the participants' their listening skill was improved considerably thanks to using YouTube videos. A majority of students said that watching YouTube videos regularly made them more proficient in spoken language, and they felt more confident in comprehending spoken English after watching YouTube videos. Additionally, a great number of students shared that they could understand conversations of native speakers better due to watching YouTube videos frequently. That was the reason why their listening abilities had improved significantly since they applied YouTube videos into their learning routine. They emphasized that the more time they watched YouTube videos, the much progress they had made in their listening skill.

Besides, the research results showed that watching YouTube videos helped students learn new words in different topics. Many participants believed that its videos contributed to expanding their word stock, which led to enriching their lexis. Most of the respondents found that the settings in its clips helped them understand the meanings of new words easily. This encouraged them to actively use new words from the videos in their daily communication. More importantly, students had good chances to acquire new words in their interested field quickly.

From the interview results, five participants confirmed that YouTube videos could help them improve their listening skill and pronunciation as well. Thanks to watching these clips, they could predict word meanings in different contexts. In case of not catching the speakers' points, they could play the videos again. Depending on their levels, they had a wide range of choice, from easy videos to difficult ones. Especially, they had good chances to listen to native speakers with various accents in many parts of the world. From that, they could imitate and adjust their pronunciation appropriately.

However, interviewees found that watching YouTube videos revealed some drawbacks. Particularly, it took them much time to search for suitable videos with their learning topics and levels. They added that many videos' contents were not appropriate to them, and even more violent, which affected their behavior. These students also indicated that watching videos too long could make them get headache and influence their health and learning. Besides, they modified that they could only watch clips on YouTube at a place where there was a strong internet connection. Therefore, at crowded places where there was a high need of internet access, watching its videos became impossible. Another challenge was that the native speakers in videos talked too fast for students to catch their points. This made weak listeners feel confused and bored. Many clips were more suitable for entertainment than learning. Thus, they sometimes made students distract their learning goals.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Conclusion

It can be concluded that YouTube videos are very useful for listening skill improvement. Most students indicate that its clips help them proficient in English spoken language, which makes them confident in communication. Additionally, videos on YouTube give them good chances to practice their listening skill. From that, their vocabulary and pronunciation are enhanced dramatically. The results of the survey and the in-depth interview show that YouTube videos are very convenient and have a wide range of choice. They can select clips appropriate with their levels and replay them some time later. However, not all videos are suitable for students' learning. Many clips are even violent, which have bad effects on viewers' behavior. Sometimes, watching YouTube videos makes students addicted and badly affects on their health. Therefore, students need to exploit positive aspects of its videos and minimize their negative ones in improving their listening skill and pronunciation.

6.2. Recommendations

Teachers and students need to regard YouTube videos as a useful resource for English language teaching and learning, especially for listening skill improvement. To maximize the benefits of its videos, both educators and learners need to carefully select its clips appropriate with teaching and learning topics as well as students' levels. Besides, the teachers should guide students how to search for its videos effectively. This helps them save much time in finding suitable clips on YouTube.

Another important point is that both teachers and students need to have positive attitudes on YouTube videos in teaching and learning listening skill. Although not all of its clips are thoroughly good for listening classes with different levels, many of them at least have educational and scientific values. Thus, teachers need to orientate and stimulate students to effectively exploit potential benefits of its videos in developing their listening skill.

7. LIMITATIONS

The paper certainly has some drawbacks in the study process. Firstly, the scope of research is conducted at Nguyen Tat Thanh University only, and its participants are EFL juniors, not for all students. Secondly, the research is carried out at one university, which may not generalize and apply its findings to other universities and institutions. Thirdly, the sample size consists of only 80 students, which may not fully represent the various perspectives and experiences of educators in similar contexts. Lastly, the study focuses exclusively on students, leaving out the attitudes and experiences of teachers, which could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of YouTube videos on the listening skill improvement.

8. FURTHER RESEARCH

The future research should examine larger and more diverse samples, and include both teachers and students at schools in Vietnam to provide a more comprehensive view about the impact of YouTube videos on English language skills such as speaking, listening and writing in EFL classrooms. Additionally, the research may expand to other different levels from high schools to university.

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